

SELF-AWARENESS: ITS EFFECTIVENESS TO CONTROL SCHOOL PERFORMANCES OF STEM 11 STUDENTS IN MINDANAO STATE UNIVERSITY-SULU, SOUTHERN PHILIPPINES

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the effectiveness of self-awareness in controlling the school performances of students at Mindanao State University-Sulu. Specifically, this aims to ascertain its effectiveness for STEM 11 students when handling their school performances. The researchers employed a quantitative research design and a 4-point Likert scale for research instrumentation. The respondents required for this study are grade 11 STEM students, sixty male and sixty female students. The researchers started the data collection at the old biology building, then proceeded to the senior high school building. This study showed that there is an effectiveness of self-awareness in controlling the school performances of the 11th-grade students at Mindanao State University-Sulu; found there is no significant difference in the students' self-awareness for controlling their school performances concerning their age and gender; and found there is a significant relationship between the three sub-categories under school performances. The students have strongly agreed to be self-aware in their performance, behavior, and financial management. Therefore, the study found that STEM 11 students at Mindanao State University-Sulu are self-aware regarding their school performance, regardless of their age or gender, which leads to better outcomes. The researchers recommend educational establishments like Mindanao State University-Sulu implement initiatives meant enhancing self-awareness among STEM students, encourage school employees, especially teachers, to serve as positive role models of self-awareness, urge students to set aside introspection for regular self-reflection, suggest parents invest in self-reflection to improve self-awareness, and advise future researchers to research how self-awareness can impact other areas to unveil new insights.

Keywords: *Self-Awareness, Student Performance, Student Behavior, Financial Management, Student's School Performance*

INTRODUCTION

Self-awareness refers to having a conscious knowledge of one's character, feelings, motives, and desires. Psychologists proposed a definition that emphasizes the ability to focus on oneself and evaluate whether one's actions, thoughts, or emotions align with internal standards. Highly self-aware individuals can objectively assess themselves, manage their emotions, align their behavior with their values and accurately perceive how others view them. The importance of self-awareness in everyday functioning, participation, and rehabilitation outcomes cannot be underestimated. It involves recognizing and evaluating performance errors as well as understanding one's strengths and limitations. These skills make it easier to identify patterns in both internal and external environments and respond accordingly. Self-awareness is a personal competency skill and it holds value in both personal and societal contexts. Ultimately it is a crucial aspect of emotional intelligence.

The effects of self-awareness are significant for our behavior satisfaction and performance (Carden et al. 2022). It plays a role in enhancing decision-making abilities and team performance (Dierdorff & Rubin, 2015) improving leadership success (Showry & Manasa, 2014), and creating more opportunities for career growth (Axelrod, 2012). Self-awareness brings about various psychological advantages including improved self-regulation greater consideration for others' needs (pro-sociality) and reduced stress and anxiety (Rasheed et al. 2019). It influences behaviors and outcomes through internal states like self-confidence and self-identity as well as the accuracy of how we perceive ourselves and how we believe others perceive us. Individuals with low self-awareness tend to resort to self-protective mechanisms such as denial withdrawal self-aggrandizement and fear of failure. As self-awareness increases individuals become more resilient and adept at adaptive performance which involves analyzing uncertain and stressful situations, identifying potential solutions, improvising, and maintaining composure (Park & Park, 2019). The study of student performance in schools is a highly debated topic in educational research. It has received significant attention in recent decades due to its importance and complexity. This issue is of great concern to students, parents, teachers, and authorities not only in our country but also in various Latin American countries and other continents (Lamas, 2015).

The researchers indulged in conducting this study to help the students of Mindanao State University-Sulu find out and understand the importance self-awareness. Through this study the students will be able to know how self-awareness can help them to hold control in terms of their school performances, specifically the student's performance, behavior, and financial management. In other words, those who will be able to possess high self-awareness can interpret their actions, feelings, and thoughts objectively. This study tended to raise contribution on the interpretation of Self-awareness to further expand its significance and benefits, that can be nourished by the students to assist them in their school performances, associated to character development for future endeavors.

With this study, the researchers are expecting the students to develop their school performances with self-awareness, which may lead them to better outcomes. Developing self-awareness is not something that comes naturally; it is a skill that can be learned. Meditation, mindfulness and various forms of reflection can help in acquiring self-awareness skills. Not only that this study is about the well-developed mindset and productiveness of the students, but according to how they would be able to respond in any situation and how this study is going to be a shed of light that can enlighten their path with self-awareness. There are several studies relating to this one, however, there are only a few existing studies about how the school performances of students are a burden to handle without self-awareness, specifically how is self-awareness a huge contribution to the student's well-being to control performance, behavior, and financial management.

Subsequently, enhancing self-awareness enhances effectiveness in both personal and professional aspects of life. By being self-aware individuals refrain from making excuses for their mistakes and instead learn from them preventing similar errors from occurring in the future. With Self-awareness one can be more productive and easygoing in life, it is that self-awareness is a powerhouse of self-improvement and balance. Being productive and having emotional intelligence, it is crucial to solve problems flawlessly. Having emotional intelligence, individuals will be more capable of handling situations, problems, and trials that they might face, they can have more confidence even if they go through some circumstances, and can help advocate and educate themselves through the problems and trials that they have come to surpass. Effectively managing emotions enables individuals to navigate challenging situations without becoming overwhelmed leading to a calm demeanor and increased success. Moreover, self-awareness facilitates the alignment of personal values with goals fostering synergy between the two rather than conflict.

Hence, this study investigated to find out the effectiveness of self-awareness amongst the students of Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School STEM 11 to control school performances, inevitably, the student's performance, student's behavior, and financial management. This study also aims to know if there is a significant difference in the self-awareness of students regardless of their age and gender. Thus, the researchers are hoping that the significance of this finding will be of great help to future researchers, students, teachers, and school administrators.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The main focus of this study is to find out the significant effectiveness of self-awareness in controlling school performances of STEM 11 Students at Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions that guided the study:

1. What is the demographic profile of STEM 11 students in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age; and
 - 1.2. Gender?

2. What is the effectiveness of self-awareness to control school performances among STEM 11 students of Mindanao State University-Sulu in terms of:

2.1. Student's Performance

2.2. Student's Behavior; and

2.3. Financial Management?

3. Is there a significant difference in the self-awareness for controlling school performances among STEM 11 students of Mindanao State University-Sulu in terms of demographic profile?

4. Is there a significant relationship among the sub-categories subsumed under the effectiveness of self-awareness on controlling school performances of STEM 11 students of Mindanao State University-Sulu?

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the study

This study was conducted in Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School. The researchers began the survey in the old biology building and proceeded to the senior high school's new building. This study was held in the second semester of the academic year 2023-2024.

Research Design

The researchers determined whether there is a significant effectiveness of self-awareness to control school performances of STEM 11 students in Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School, the researchers have employed the quantitative research design through descriptive method.

According to Pritha Bhandari (2023), Quantitative research involves gathering and examining numerical data. It helps identify trends, make predictions, test cause-and-effect relationships, and draw conclusions that apply to larger groups. (Sirisilla, 2023). Descriptive research design is an effective method employed by researchers to acquire data on a precise group. This approach offers a comprehensive depiction of the traits and actions exhibited by a particular population or subject. With observation and data collection descriptive research aids in enhancing comprehension of a specific problem and offers essential insights that can guide future investigations.

Sampling Design

The sampling used in this research was stratified sampling, as the researchers divided the respondents' population into two based on the gender of the grade 11 students in the Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics strand. One-hundred and sixty (160) students were accumulated as the subjects.

Research Instrument

The researchers have employed a self-developed survey questionnaire to obtain data and information regarding the effectiveness of self-awareness in controlling school performances among STEM 11 students in Mindanao State University-Sulu. A questionnaire is a research tool containing a series of questions designed to obtain standardized responses from the respondents (Sir Francis Galton).

The questionnaire consists of 2 parts. The first part asked for the demographic profile of the respondents, such as their name (optional), age, and gender. On the other hand, the second part comprised questions regarding the effectiveness of self-awareness in controlling school performances in terms of student's performance, students' behavior, and financial management. The respondents indicated their answer using a 4-point Likert scale- (1) Strongly Agree; (2) Agree; (3) Disagree; (4) Strongly Disagree.

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Statistical Treatment of Data

A descriptive statistical tool was appropriately employed in the treatment of data to be gathered for this study, namely:

1. For research number one (1) Frequency counts and percentages will be employed to determine the profile of Senior High School STEM Students.
2. For research number two (2) Mean and standard deviation will be employed to determine the extent of challenges encountered in learning science among senior high school STEM students of Sulu College of Technology Inc. during the School Year 2021-2022.
3. For research problem number three (3) T-tests for independent samples will be employed to determine the significant differences in the extent of Challenges encountered in learning science among senior high school STEM students of Sulu College of Technology Inc. when they are grouped according to gender. One-way Analysis of variance (ANOVA) will be employed to determine the significant differences when they are grouped according to age, parents' average monthly income, and parents' educational attainment.

4. For research problem number four (4) Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson's r) will be employed to determine the degree of correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of Challenges encountered in learning science among senior high school STEM students of Sulu College of Technology Inc.

Scope and Delimitation

This study focuses on self-awareness in controlling school performances of grade 11 STEM students at Mindanao State University-Sulu. The respondent of this study is delimited to the Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics students of Mindanao State University-Sulu during the school year 2023-2024

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. *What is the demographic profile of STEM 11 students in terms of:*

1.1. *Age; and*

1.2. *Gender?*

Table 1.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
16-years-old and below	36	30.0
17-years-old and above	84	70.0
Total	120	100.0

Table 1.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Table 1.1 shows the demographic profile of STEM 11 students in Mindanao State University-Sulu in terms of their age. The result shows that students 16 years old and below obtained a frequency of 36 equivalent to 30% of the respondents, while the respondents who are 17 years old and above garnered a frequency of 84 which is 70% of the respondents. This means that the students 17 years old and above are greater in number rather than the students 16 years old and below.

Table 1.2 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	60	50.0
Female	60	50.0
Total	120	100.0

Table 1.2 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Gender

Table 1.2 shows the result for the demographic profile of the STEM 11 students in terms of gender and was shown to be equal (*Male* = 50% and *Female* = 50%) as the number of respondents was divided into two.

2. What is the effectiveness of self-awareness to control school performances among STEM 11 students of Mindanao State University-Sulu in terms of:

2.1. Student's Performance

2.2. Student's Behavior; and

2.3. Financial Management?

Table 2.1 Effectiveness of Self-awareness in Controlling School Performances in terms of Student's Performance.

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
1. As a student, I am aware of how I manage my school assignments and projects.	3.6	0.5	Strongly Agree
2. I am aware of the ticking clock, and perfectly manage my pending tasks on time.	3.5	0.5	Strongly Agree
3. I finish my tasks accordingly, as I'm aware of how they could affect my grades.	3.4	0.7	Strongly Agree
4. I am aware of how difficult oral recitation is, that is why I study my lessons objectively	3.4	0.5	Strongly Agree
5. I am aware of my topics in report presentations, that is why I explain them very well to the class.	3.4	0.6	Strongly Agree
6. I am aware that it's better not to cram, so I refrain from doing all the given works the night before its deadline.	3.4	0.6	Strongly Agree
7. I am aware of what might disappoint me, therefore I review my lessons to avoid from getting low scores in quizzes and exams.	3.3	0.6	Strongly Agree
8. I am aware of how important group grades are, so I participate during group activity to assure we'll get high scores.	3.3	0.6	Strongly Agree
9. I am aware that every point counts, therefore I usually put extra efforts when making an output, to make sure I'll receive high scores.	3.1	0.7	Agree
10. I am aware of how significant exposure in terms of academics is, so I join school contests for experience and also to enhance my skills.	3.0	0.7	Agree
Total	3.3	0.6	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.75 = SD; 1.76-2.50 = D; 2.51-3.25= A; 3.26-4.00 = SA

Table 2.1 shows the total result that the students strongly agreed with the survey questionnaire given with a grand mean of 3.3 (SD=0.6), which implies that self-awareness effectively controls the student's performance.

Thus, the students are more self-aware in managing their school assignments and projects, as it gained the highest mean of 3.6 (SD = 0.5) which indicates that the students have strongly agreed and less on being aware of the significance of academic exposure and experiences, which turned to have the lowest mean of 3.0 (SD = 0.7), indicating that

they agreed. Thus, self-awareness plays a vital role in the students to help them achieve better outcomes throughout their journey as students.

Table 2.2 Effectiveness of Self-awareness in Controlling School Performances in terms of Student's Behavior.

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
1. I am aware of the school's rules and regulations, and I am doing my best to be a great student.	3.6	0.5	Strongly Agree
2. I am aware that I should watch my words carefully, when talking to the teachers and even to my fellow students.	3.6	0.6	Strongly Agree
3. I am aware how teachers contribute to my well-being as a student and an individual, so I always listen to the teacher during discussion.	3.5	0.6	Strongly Agree
4. I am aware of my role as a student, so I set boundaries with my teachers.	3.5	0.7	Strongly Agree
5. I always put my trashes in the proper place because I know it's the right thing to do.	3.4	0.7	Strongly Agree
6. I am aware to always show respect, and I refrain myself from talking with my seatmates while the teacher is in front of the class.	3.4	0.7	Strongly Agree
7. I am aware of how I should behave inside and outside the classroom.	3.4	0.7	Strongly Agree
8. I am aware of my schedule, that is why I practice proper time management.	3.4	0.7	Strongly Agree
9. I am aware of my obligation as a student, so I participate in group activities.	3.4	0.6	Strongly Agree
10. I am aware of how I should mangle with my classmates, properly.	3.3	0.6	Strongly Agree
Total	3.4	0.6	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.75 = SD; 1.76-2.50 = D; 2.51-3.25= A; 3.26-4.00 = SA

Table 2.2 displays a total grand mean of 3.4 (SD=0.6), indicating that the students have strongly agreed, which implies that self-awareness is effective for the students' behavior as they strongly agreed to be aware of the proper behavior they need to practice and show given that they are students and an individual in a community.

Subsequently, the students are more self-aware of the proper behavior towards the school rules and regulations, as it garnered the highest mean of 3.6 (SD= 0.5) indicating that they strongly agreed, and less on being aware of the proper behavior when mangling with their classmates, as it resulted to be the lowest mean of 3.3 (SD= 0.6) which also indicates that they strongly agreed.

Table 2.3 Effectiveness of Self-awareness in Controlling School Performances in terms of Financial Management.

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
1. I am aware of my family's financial status.	3.5	0.6	Strongly Agree
2. I am aware that money is hard to look for, so I refrain from buying things that isn't necessary.	3.4	0.7	Strongly Agree
3. I am aware of saving money, to use for future purposes.	3.4	0.7	Strongly Agree
4. I am aware that I should only buy the things that I needed and less on what I wanted.	3.4	0.7	Strongly Agree
5. I am aware that I should be productive and careful with my money to avoid shortage.	3.4	0.7	Strongly Agree
6. I am aware of how I should handle school related expenses.	3.4	0.6	Strongly Agree
7. I am aware of how I should manage my allowance.	3.4	0.7	Strongly Agree
8. I am aware of how I should spend my money at school.	3.3	0.7	Strongly Agree
9. I am aware that my class funds might grow overtime, therefore I pay for the contributions in class on time to avoid conflicts.	3.3	0.6	Strongly Agree
10. I am aware that money is important, so I don't buy snacks when I'm full.	3.2	0.8	Agree
Total	3.4	0.7	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.75 = SD; 1.76-2.50 = D; 2.51-3.25= A; 3.26-4.00 = SA

Table 2.3 reveals a total grand mean of 3.4 (SD= 0.7) which indicates that the students have strongly agreed, and implies that the students have an effective self-awareness in controlling their financial management.

Moreover, the students strongly agreed to be self-aware of their family's financial status as it gained the highest mean of 3.5 (SD = 0.6) and agreed to be aware of the importance of money as it gained the lowest mean of 3.2 (SD= 0.8). Overall, self-awareness is effective for their financial management as they are aware of how they should approach circumstances to properly manage their financial activities.

Overall, table 2.1- table 2.3 displays the effectiveness of self-awareness to control school performances among STEM 11 students of Mindanao State University-Sulu in terms of the Student's Performance ($M = 3.3$, $SD = 0.6$), Student's behavior ($M = 3.4$, $SD = 0.6$) the student's financial management ($M = 3.4$, $SD = 0.7$). This amplifies that STEM 11 students of Mindanao State University-Sulu have highly proven the effectiveness of self-awareness in controlling their school performances, as the respondents gained a total of 3.4 Grand Mean ($SD = 0.6$) simply conveys that the students have most likely "Strongly Agreed" to be self-aware in accordance to the questionnaires. The students are aware of the things that must be done as they work for their studies, with that self-awareness has proven that the students effectively assess themselves to think ahead of time and watch their actions and behavior, specifically to watch over and take control of their school performances.

According to Colthorpe (2015), a proficient self-regulated, and self-aware learner will simultaneously restructure their ideas, feelings, and behaviors to maximize learning

and employ a variety of tactics for efficient problem-solving and learning. It has been proposed by Baber (2010) that people who possess a strong sense of self-awareness are better equipped to handle obstacles in their lives. Conversely, a low feeling of self-efficacy "may lead an individual to overestimate their skills and abilities, resulting in views of challenging tasks as obstacles to be avoided."

3. *Is there a significant difference in the self-awareness for controlling school performances among STEM 11 students of Mindanao State University-Sulu in terms of demographic profile?*

TABLE 3.1 Significant Difference in Self-awareness for Controlling School Performances in Terms of Age

Measure	16 years old and below		17 years old and above		t(118)	p-value
	M	SD	M	SD		
Age	3.3	0.3	3.4	0.3	-0.939	.350

**Significant at $p < 0.05$*

An independent sample t-test was performed to compare the self-awareness for controlling school performances of students in terms of their age. Table 3.1 displays that there is no significant difference in the self-awareness for controlling school performances of STEM 11 students in terms of their age between students aged 16 years old and below ($M = 3.3$, $SD = 0.3$) and students aged 17 years old and above ($M = 3.4$, $SD = 0.3$) having a p-value of .350; $t(118) = -0.939$, that helped the researchers determined that the hypothesis is being accepted. This indicates that the self-awareness of the students does not depend on their age but rather on their capabilities and maturity which leads them to better expectations and situations by being self-aware.

This claim is supported by Tamar (2022) that self-awareness is a fundamental milestone of psychological development that is a key part of the human condition. A person can recognize their own mental states, emotions, and behaviors, and to understand how they are perceived by others. It is a complex cognitive process that develops gradually from childhood and into adulthood. As young children progress through adolescence, they become increasingly more aware of their thoughts and emotions, as well as those of others. Additionally, the ability to self-reflect and engage in introspection becomes more sophisticated as they age. Because of their learning and thinking differences, children who do not develop self-awareness are at a disadvantage. When children are self-aware, they have a feeling of their strengths and weaknesses. To be successful, they must know what their strengths are, as well as what they must improve on. Tamar (2022).

TABLE 3.2 Significant Difference in the Self-awareness for Controlling School Performances in terms of Gender

Variable	Male		Female		t(118)	p-value
	M	SD	M	SD		
Gender	3.4	0.3	3.4	0.3	-.394	.695

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

An independent sample t-test was performed to compare the self-awareness for controlling school performances between male and female students. Table 3.2 represents that there is no significant difference in the self-awareness for controlling school performances of STEM 11 students between male ($M = 3.4$, $SD = 0.3$) and female respondents ($M = 3.4$, $SD = 0.3$) that gained a p-value of .695; $t(118) = -.394$, that guided the researchers to determine that the hypothesis is being accepted. This implies that gender difference is not found to be a concern in the means of self-awareness, as both genders effectively assess themselves with self-awareness to aim and achieve better school performance.

This result is supported by Myint & Aung, (2016) stated that according to a study done in Myanmar, there is no discernible difference between male and female EI and self-awareness. It's noteworthy to notice that, statistically speaking, both genders agree that sometimes it's better to learn how to be impolite than to save someone's face. Women and men alike are willing to acquire the skill of being unpleasant in a foreign language and see it as essential (Ahmadi & Heydari Soureshjani, 2011).

4. Is there a significant relationship among the sub-categories subsumed under the effectiveness of self-awareness on controlling school performances of STEM 11 students of Mindanao State University-Sulu?

TABLE 4 Relationship of Student's Performance, Student's Behavior and Financial Management

Variables	1	2	3
Student's Performance	-		
Student's Behavior	.587**	-	
Financial Management	.329**	.596**	-

Note: * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Pearson correlation was utilized to determine the significant relationship among the sub-categories subsumed under the effect of self-awareness on controlling school performances of STEM 11 students of Mindanao State University-Sulu. Table 4 demonstrates the correlation of the sub-categories subsumed, which are the Student's Performance, Student's Behavior, and Financial Management, it is found that the Student's Performance has a potential Pearson correlation of moderate positive (negative) correlation ($r = .587^{**}$) when correlate to Student's Behavior and low positive (negative) correlation ($r = .329^{**}$) with Financial Management, and the Student's Behavior with a moderate positive (negative) correlation ($r = .596^{**}$) with Financial Management and vice versa. A sig value of .000 is less when compared to the alpha level of .05, which

simply means that the null hypothesis is rejected and that the Student's Performance, Student's Behavior, and Financial Management have a significant relationship. Subsequently, the relationship between the variables implies that self-awareness plays a significant role in the student's school performance, thus, the student's performance, behavior, and financial management may affect the school performance of the students if not supported by self-awareness. Moreover, the significant relationship and connection among the indicators are to show the effectiveness of self-awareness in controlling the student's school performances.

A person's performance, especially academic achievement, is greatly influenced by several variables, such as motivation, emotion, and surroundings (Garkaz et al., 2011). As stated by Rogel, I.R. (2012) notes a student's behavior, whether it be academic or otherwise, has a significant role in determining their academic progress among the many aspects impacting academic achievement for achieving the best possible school performance. It encompasses a student's perspective, decision-making, perseverance, learning attempts, and interpersonal interactions with members of the school community. Budgeting, self-control, and awareness can help students reduce their consumption while maintaining the flexibility needed to handle unforeseen circumstances, claims Simone Galperti's *The Theory of Personal Budgeting* (2019).

Conclusions

The researchers in this study have accumulated a total population of one-hundred twenty (120) students, with an equal distribution of both genders comprised of 60 male and 60 female respondents of which 36 are 16 years old and below while 84 are 17 years old and above, meaning that the students 17 years old and above are greater in number rather than the students 16 years old and below, for the research entitled "Self-awareness; Its Effectiveness to Control School Performances of STEM 11 students in Mindanao State University-Sulu".

According to the results, it is found that the students have strongly agreed to be self-aware in managing their school assignments and projects, and their pending tasks on time and accordingly, as they identify how these could affect their grades, including oral recitations and report presentations. The students avoid finishing their work the night before the submission or deadline, review their lessons to avoid low scores on quizzes and exams, and participate in group activities to achieve high scores and grades. And have agreed to be aware that every point they make counts and that academic exposure and experiences are significant in terms of the Student's Performance. The student's behavior, on the other hand, the students turned out to have strongly agreed with all the given question information under the variable. The students strongly agreed to be aware of the behavior that they need to wear as students, specifically towards the school's rules and regulations, to always show respect when talking to their teachers and fellow students, listening to the teachers during the discussion, their role as students towards their schedules, their behavior inside and outside the classroom to be exact which is putting the trash to its proper place, their obligation as students, and how they should properly mingle with their classmates. Moreover, in the financial management, the result

showed that the students strongly agreed on being aware of their family's financial status, that they are aware to refrain from spending on unnecessary things, saving money for future purposes, and only buying the things that are needed and rather than their wants, being productive and careful to avoid shortage which they properly handle their school-related expenses, managing allowance, also aware of how they should spend money at school, paying for class funds in time to avoid conflicts and have agreed to being aware of the importance of money. Thus, this indicates that the students have effective self-awareness as it turned out that they strongly agreed with the situations and circumstances. This perceived self-awareness made them more productive and organized in the means of their study and their youth as students.

Furthermore, it is found that there is no significant difference in the self-awareness for controlling school performances among STEM 11 students in terms of demographic profile. The students' self-awareness does not depend on their respective age and gender but rather on their maturity and abilities to respond to circumstances, specifically the students effectively assess themselves with their perceived self-awareness, as they are aware of the appropriate behavior that needs to be applied in their everyday outgoing and also found out that the students have effective management in the state of their financial activities. In addition, the students' performance, behavior, and time management having significant relationships indicates that the students are highly self-aware as they control their school performances which justly implies the capabilities of the students to aim for better school performance outcomes through the effectiveness of self-awareness.

Hence, the study has proven that the STEM 11 students in Mindanao State University-Sulu are self-aware of the means of their school performances regardless of their age and gender, the students are aware of how to control their school performances which leads them to better expectations and outcomes.

Recommendations

This study recommends the following:

1. The researchers suggest that educational establishments, such as Mindanao State University-Sulu, carry out initiatives and treatments meant to encourage self-awareness among students. These programs could consist of seminars, workshops, or therapy sessions aimed at enhancing goal-setting, emotional intelligence, and self-reflection abilities.
2. Encourage teachers and other school employees to serve as positive role models of self-awareness. Demonstrate self-reflection, emotional intelligence, and open communication in interactions with the students. This sets an example for them to follow.
3. The researchers recommend promoting regular self-reflection by encouraging students to set aside specific time to introspect. This could involve reflecting on

their acts and behaviors and asking questions concerning their values, goals, and aspirations.

4. To improve self-awareness as a parent, take time for self-reflection to understand emotions, reactions, and circumstances that trigger parenting situations. Consider how own experiences and beliefs may influence parent's decisions. These practices were to enhance self-awareness, strengthen bonds with children and will help parents become more effective and conscious.
5. For future researchers, research about how self-awareness impacts various areas like education, psychology, and even business. This can uncover new insights. Future researchers can explore cross-cultural studies on self-awareness to understand how self-awareness practices differ across cultures and their impact

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The purpose of this study was to gather insights and understand the effectiveness of self-awareness on the school performances of STEM 11 students. The researchers sought informed consent from all the respondents and ensured that they fully understood the purpose and procedure of the study.

The researchers have assessed and addressed ethical issues regarding the study, and have prioritized the well-being and rights of the respondents. The data collected was used for research purposes only and remained confidential. The participation of the students was only voluntary, ensuring their response was anonymous.

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REFERENCES

- Ahmadi, &. H. (2011). Does Emotional Intelligence Depend on Gender? A Study on Undergraduate English Majors of Three Iranian Universities.
<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/2158244017725796>
- Axelrod. (2012). Defining Self-Awareness in the Context of Adult Development: A Systematic Literature Review. *Journal of Management Education*, 140-177.
[https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=Defining+Self-Awareness++in+the+Context+of+Adult++Development%3A++A+Systematic+Literature+%00review&btnG=""\ |d=gs_qabs&t=1703328693539&u=%23p%3D38rhxnryM3MJ](https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=Defining+Self-Awareness++in+the+Context+of+Adult++Development%3A++A+Systematic+Literature+%00review&btnG=)
- Baber, e. (2010). USING AND DOING SCIENCE: GENDER, SELF-EFFICACY, AND SCIENCE IDENTITY OF UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS IN STEM. 32.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/270468372_Using_and_doing_science

- _gender_self-
efficacy_and_science_identity_of_undergraduate_students_in_STEM
- Bhandari, P. (2023). What Is Quantitative Research? | Definition, Uses & Methods. 7. <https://www.scribbr.com/author/pritha/page/7/>
- Carden, J. (2022). Defining Self-Awareness in the Context of Adult Development: A Systematic Literature Review. *Journal of Management Education*, 140-177. [https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=Defining+Self-Awareness++in+the+Context+of+Adult++Development%3A++A+Systematic+Literature+%00review&btnG=" \ | "d=gs_qabs&t=1703328693539&u=%23p%3D38rhxnryM3MJ](https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=Defining+Self-Awareness++in+the+Context+of+Adult++Development%3A++A+Systematic+Literature+%00review&btnG=)
- Colthorpe, K. S. (2018). A Review of Self-Regulated Learning and Self-Efficacy: The Key to Tertiary Transition in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348569019_A_Review_of_Self-Regulated_Learning_and_Self-Efficacy_The_Key_to_Tertiary_Transition_in_Science_Technology_Engineering_and_Mathematics_STEM
- Galperti, S. (2019). A Theory of Personal Budgeting. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.3982/TE2881>
- Garkaz, M. B. (2011). ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT STUDENTS IN A STATE UNIVERSITY IN THE PHILIPPINES: INPUTS TO THE NEW BASIC EDUCATION CURRICULUM. <https://smrj.nemsu.edu.ph/index.php/SMRJ/article/download/227/160>
- Lamas, H. A. (2015). School Performance. Sobre el rendimiento escolar, 1-30. <https://www.bing.com/ck/a?!&&p=07622b7de6f54b14JmItdHM9MTcxMDcyMDAwMCZpZ3VpZD0zOTRiMGI4Ni0wM2Y5LTZIOWQtMjY3OS0xODVjMDI3YjZmNDMmaW5zaWQ9NTIxMA&ptn=3&ver=2&hsh=3&fclid=394b0b86-03f9-6e9d-2679-185c027b6f43&psq=hector+a+lamas+2015&u=a1aHR0cHM6Ly9maWxlcy5lcmIjLmVkJmdvdi9mdWxsdGV4dC9FSjExMzUzNTAucGRm&ntb=1>
- Myint, A. &. (2016). The Relationship Between Emotional Intelligence and Job Performance of Myanmar School Teachers. Department of Educational Psychology Yangon University of Education, Myanmar. <https://po.pnuresearchportal.org/ejournal/index.php/asten/article/view/142/124>
- Park, P. &. (2019). Adaptability: The Foundation of Adaptability and How to Implement it in Practice. <https://www.ckju.net/en/dossier/adaptability-foundation-adaptability-and-how-implement-it-practice>
- Rasheed, e. (2019). The Development of a Self-Awareness Skill for High School Students with the Process of Social and Emotional Learning. 1-14. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1362064.pdf>
- Showry, a. M. (2014). Defining Self-Awareness in the Context of Adult Development: A Systematic Literature Review. *Journal of Management Education*, 140-177. [https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=Defining+Self-Awareness++in+the+Context+of+Adult++Development%3A++A+Systematic+Literature+%00review&btnG=" \ | "d=gs_qabs&t=1703328693539&u=%23p%3D38rhxnryM3MJ](https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=Defining+Self-Awareness++in+the+Context+of+Adult++Development%3A++A+Systematic+Literature+%00review&btnG=)

Tamar, J. (2022). What Age Does Self-Awareness Begin to Develop? An Exploration of the Milestone of Psychological Development . Self-Awareness.
<https://www.breakoutofthebox.com/at-what-age-does-self-awareness-begin-to-develop-an-exploration-of-the-milestone-of-psychological-developmedesig>